

BIBLIOGRAPHY

For successfully completing my project file, I have taken the data from the following website link/ URL. This particular project was accepted by the

i) INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TOXICOLOGICAL & PHARMACOLOGICAL RESEARCH.

ii) REVIEW OF CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY & PHARMACOKINETICS.

Project Name:

RETROSPECTIVE BIostatistical ANALYSIS DATA FOR ESTABLISHING SAFETY IN MONOTHERAPY INVOLVING LIFE SAVING DRUGS (ESTABLISHMENT OF SAFETY IN THE CONTEXT OF MONOTHERAPY INVOLVING LIFE SAVING DRUGS).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14194422>

Details of Website/ URL (Reference):

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.27721590>

Wikipedia.

GOOGLE SCHOLAR.